

MODELLING NANOSCALE GRAPHENE STRUCTURES USING A MULTI-PHYSICS MOLECULAR-DYNAMICS FINITE-ELEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

New 2D materials (e.g. graphene) are leading to a new class of 3D-layered hybrid materials, with controllably designed atomic structures. Scalable processes (e.g. vapour deposition) synthesise meter-scale bulk of these nano-sized featured materials, which have many potential applications in next-generation structural graphene-based composites, electronics, sensors, DNA sequencing or desalination membranes.

The numerical design of nano-materials and devices of varying architectures and dimensions constitutes a clear and increasingly important need, but requires the development of physically-accurate and numerically-efficient modelling approaches. While Molecular Dynamics (MD) can exhibit unfavourable numerical scaling, more computationally affordable methods, such as continuum-based Finite Element Method (FEM), inherently struggle to capture governing discrete phenomena (e.g. fracture-nucleation).

We propose (i) a Molecular Dynamics Finite Element Method (MDFEM) for the multi-physics and multi-scale numerical design of nano-materials. The MD equilibrium equations are embedded exactly within the computationally more versatile FEM. This MDFEM, shown to be equivalent to MD, readily implements any MD force field, including reactive and charge/dipole potentials, and was embedded in both standard explicit and implicit dynamic FEM codes, displaying linear computational scaling and a broader range of solver strategies and applicability (e.g. from femto-seconds to micro-meters); (ii) novel Objective Boundary Conditions (OBC), which account for non-local interactions with rotational periodicities of 1D/2D structures, and homogenise the response of discrete nano-systems for any continuum and structural idealisations of choice (e.g. plate theory).

The proposed MDFEM and OBC were used to (i) design pillared graphene-based composite reinforcement phases; (ii) obtain the latter's homogenised structural response; (iii) investigate the fracture toughness of cracked graphene; (iv) reduce numerical cost using its intrinsic suitability for concurrent multi-scale simulations of continuum and MD domains; (v) design multi-physics devices based on electric field induced polarisations in Carbon Nanotubes (CNT) and porous graphene. Finally, the proposed MDFEM and OBC constitute a comprehensive framework for the virtual engineering design and tailoring of nano-material, structures and devices to target multi-functional properties, for a range of applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The continuous and accelerating rise of 2D materials comprises the advent of a new paradigm in 3D-layered material design and device development across all scales, potentially offering unprecedented properties and functionalities in almost all engineering technology applications [1–3]. With atomic structures controllably designed, assembled and optimised at the nano-scale, properties of multi-functional devices and material structures may soon be tailored to target specifications at the desired scale.

Recent and ongoing progress in manufacturing processes, most notably scalable Roll-to-Roll (R2R) based Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) and Nanoimprint Litography, allow for the meter-scale synthesis of bulk nano-materials with engineered nanometer-sized features. Novel design concepts, such

as 3D Pillared Graphene (PGS) [4] for instance, hold a high transformative potential for nano-layer reinforced structural composites, due to their predicted outstanding 3D mechanical properties [5]. Additionally, Lithium-doped PGS are expected to have unique hydrogen storage capacities above 6 wt% [6], due to the alkali ion's charge-induced dipoles in the H_2 ; potentially offering the first commercially viable material for H_2 -fuelled mobile applications (e.g. cars, phones).

This nano-manufacturing progress offers novel design possibilities, creating a new and increasingly important need for corresponding physically accurate and numerically efficient modelling methods. Given an unprecedented scope in design space, the virtual design and optimisation becomes of paramount importance, if time-to-market of material developments is to be accelerated as aimed for by the US Materials Genome Initiative [7]. Modelling large complex atomic structures is unaffordable with Quantum Mechanics (QM) or even Molecular Dynamics (MD). However, computationally affordable continuum based methods, such as the Finite Element Method (FEM), inherently struggle to capture important discrete physical features (e.g. lattice defects), which govern critical phenomena (e.g. fracture nucleation).

The MD method has increasingly been embedded in the FEM [8–12], particularly for structural simulations, as the equilibrium equations of MD and FEM can be expressed in equivalent forms. The resulting MDFEM is computationally more favourable and versatile than MD [9], while offering increased integration compatibility for multi-scale simulations with larger scale continuum FEM. Readily available, structural mechanics FEM elements (e.g. springs, beams) have been used for MDFEM [11, 12]. However, their use is detrimental to MDFEM's full mechanical non-linear capabilities and prohibits all multi-physics. Several MDFEM proposed mechanically non-linear elements [8–10, 13] with varying flexibility in accommodating different MD force fields; yet a general, high-level multi-physics MDFEM with corresponding non-local Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) has not been proposed.

This paper (i) introduces a MDFEM [1], exactly embedding the equilibrium equations of any multi-physics MD force field within the computationally more favourable FEM, for modelling any 3D nano-structures and load cases, using the simplest element topologies; (ii) derives novel Objective Boundary Conditions (OBC) [2], which exactly represent rotational symmetries in 1D/2D structures with local and non-local physics, and homogenise their multi-physics response for any chosen continuum idealisation.

The key novel aspects of the proposed formulations, which represent new contributions to the state of the art, are: (i) a mathematically robust multi-physics MDFEM derivation; (ii) the formal separation of force field and element topology information; (iii) the differentiation between constitutive, geometrical and mixed instabilities; (iv) a mathematically and numerically optimised implementation; (v) a symbolic processor based implementation for a fast and high-level MDFEM implementation; (vi) both explicit and implicit FEM formulations, where the latter allows for large time and spacial scales, eigenvalue analyses, and a singular mass matrix; (vii) the new OBC, which implement local and non-local interactions in low-dimensional structures under generic torsion/bending deformations; (viii) the ability for readily and implicitly obtaining equivalent homogenised properties of discrete structures.

The proposed multi-physics and multi-scale compatible MDFEM is equivalent to MD, as shown by the analyses of brittle fracture in Carbon Nanotubes (CNT) with defects, but at a reduced computational cost. Electro-mechanical examples of electric field induced polarisations in CNT and charge distribution in graphene as well as examples of concurrently coupled MD and continuum FEM domains demonstrate the MDFEM to be well suited for both multi-scale and multi-physics modelling. Using the OBC, homogenised mechanical properties for PGS are obtained, which allows the MDFEM to design graphene nano-structures to target property specifications in a parametric study approach. A numerical study of a sample porous graphene-sensor, which may find applications in desalination or personal DNA-sequencing devices, is presented. Finally, by eigenvalue-based modelling of buckling, failure, vibrational, piezoelectric and electric-field induced polarisation behaviours, among others, this MDFEM with its OBC can contribute to the design of nano-scale graphene composites, sensors, H_2 storage and other multi-functional nano-materials.

2 DYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM IN A GENERALISED MULTI-PHYSICS DOMAIN

2.1 Hamilton's Principle & Lagrange's Equation in a Generalised Domain

Hamilton's Principle is a formal and natural approach to describe dynamic equilibrium in a discrete or discretised multi-physics system, and can lead to Lagrange's equation by a Legendre Transform:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial (T^*(\dot{\mathbf{q}}))}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}} \right)^T + \left(\frac{\partial (V(\mathbf{q}))}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \right)^T = \frac{d}{dt} (\nabla_{\dot{\mathbf{q}}} (T^*(\dot{\mathbf{q}}))) + \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} (V(\mathbf{q})) = \mathbf{f}, \quad (1)$$

where the system's n generalised displacements are denoted by $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, the corresponding generalised external forces performing work on the system by $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, the multi-physics conservative generalised potential energy by V and, the generalised kinetic co-energy by T^* .

2.2 A discrete Molecular Dynamics Finite Element Method (MDFEM)

At the MD level of theory, the set of translational displacements, \mathbf{u} , partial electric charges, \mathbf{q} , and electric dipoles, \mathbf{p} , of all atoms constitutes a comprehensive and natural choice of \mathbf{q} for a discrete particle system, as show in Fig. 1(a). Noting that, for a multi-physics domain, the kinetic co-energy may generally be non-quadratic and potentially positive semi-definite, it follows that Eq. (1) becomes [1]:

$$\mathbf{M}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \nabla_{\mathbf{q}} (V(\mathbf{q})) = \mathbf{M}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + (\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}}^V)^T = \mathbf{f}, \quad (2)$$

where $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} (V(\mathbf{q}))$ is the transpose of the generalised potential's Jacobian relative to the system's displacements, i.e $\nabla_{\mathbf{q}} (V(\mathbf{q})) = (\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}}^V)^T$. The generalised mass matrix, $\mathbf{M}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, is unique, symmetric, potentially non-linear, either positive definite and non-singular or, positive semi-definite and singular. Eq. (2) suggest an analogy with the FEM and can be solved using a Newton-Raphson scheme, given the generalised mass matrix, $\mathbf{M}(\dot{\mathbf{q}})$, as well as the generalised potential's Jacobian, $\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}}^V$, and Hessian, $\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{q}}^V$, relative to the system's generalised displacements can be determined [1].

2.3 Computational Chemistry Multi-Physics Force Fields

A system's MD potential energy, V , generally consists of the superposition of a set, \mathbb{S} , of sub-potentials, V_S (e.g. bond stretch, bending), where each of the latter can be sub-divided into n_p^S repeating partitions, which have varying partitioning patterns (e.g. summation over bond lengths, bond angles). Thus, the MD potential energy can be expressed as the summation over sub-potential partitions as:

$$V(\mathbf{c}) = \sum_{\mathbb{S}} V_S(\mathbf{c}_S) = \sum_{\mathbb{S}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_p^S} V_S^i(\mathbf{c}_S^i(\mathbf{r}_S^i, \mathbf{q}_S^i)), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{c} represents the potential's characteristic variables (e.g. bond lengths/angles). Classical force fields include sub-potentials for mechanical deformation modes (e.g. stretching), while reactive potentials [14] may capture bond formations and, charge-dipole potentials [15] cause electro-mechanical couplings.

Figure 1: Generalised displacements for atoms i and j and selected MD characteristic variables.

2.4 MDFEM Element Topologies & Uncoupled Constitutive and Geometrical Information

It follows naturally that each sub-potential partition takes the role of an “element” within the FEM terminology. An element topology may be created for each sub-potential partitioning pattern, which are then superposed in sub-potential layers when meshing the atomic system. The spacial superposition of multiple element topologies outlines a fundamental difference between the MDFEM [1] and the classical FEM, where element superpositioning is atypical. The smallest element topology representing one partition, V_S^i , is thus identical to the latter’s characteristic variable-defining sketch, see Fig. 1(b).

Using the FEM-typical element assembly approach, only the local Jacobian and Hessian within each partition, i.e. $\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}_S^i}^{V_S^i}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{q}_S^i}^{V_S^i}$, are required for solving Eq. (2). The latter tensors are obtained indirectly, using chain derivatives, which offers multiple advantages; most notably by uncoupling the chemical force field constitutive information from the spacial geometrical behaviour of the characteristic variables [1].

3 OBJECTIVE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR HOMOGENISING PROPERTIES OF LOW-DIMENSIONAL STRUCTURES WITH ROTATIONS, LOCAL & NON-LOCAL PHYSICS

3.1 Introduction & Challenges

Periodic structures occur frequently across many scales and wide ranges of application fields, with compounds such as crystals, single-walled carbon nanotubes or graphene commonly forming the basis of promising future technologies. Thus, the efficient numerical modelling of periodic structure is of paramount importance. Boundary Conditions capturing periodicity are a crucial and complementary component to any computational methodology, if modelling and understanding the response of periodic structures, with the ultimate aim of their reliable virtual design and optimisation, is to be achieved. Exploiting, as much as possible, internal symmetries of materials, ensures that the continuously increasing computational resources are solely spent on numerically exploring the material systems’ design space.

Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC), for compounds with translational symmetries, cannot capture rotational or more generally orthogonal symmetries. The latter increasingly occur with low-dimensional compounds, both in the base state or during loading (e.g. bending/torsion). Hence, a new and robust formulation is required [2], which faces the following challenges: (i) The periodicity between matching Unit Cell (UC) boundaries now includes orthogonal transformations; (ii) Non-local physics, where material points from several UC away interact, require accurate cumulative rotations (e.g. Van der Waals interactions in a bent planar structure); (iii) The homogenised properties must solely be based on the mean-field response of the UC, without inadvertently interfering with the natural internal UC micro-field. Fig. 2 shows a discrete or discretised domain, where material points are depicted by \bullet , matching UC boundaries by $|$, while local and non-local energy interactions are denoted by $|$ and $|$, respectively.

Figure 2: Objective structure UC with local & non-local physics during bending.

3.2 Towards Modelling Objective Structures

There is a clear need for a boundary condition formulation tailored for orthogonal symmetric structures, hereafter termed *Objective Structures* [16], which are simultaneously applicable for robust property homogenisation. Hereafter, a formulation is presented, which: (i) can account for orthogonal transformations with the resulting physics-based geometrical non-linearities; (ii) is applicable to both discrete- and continuum-physics governed domains, with both local and non-local interactions; (iii) poses no risk for artificially suppressing or altering the UC micro-field; (iv) inherently bridges the gap between scales, discrete-to-continuum as well as continuum-to-continuum through implicit property homogenisation.

3.3 Objective Boundary Conditions (OBC) with Modularly Defined UC

Hereafter, the OBC UC is formally defined [2] to be constituted of a:

1. *Physical Unit* (PU): Let a PU be a repeating, continuous or discrete, physical subdomain of an infinite structure up to orthogonal transformations, where each material point i has generalised positions, \mathbf{r}_i . The PU potential energy may additionally depend on the state of other tessellated PU units, denoted by $\mathbf{r}_{(\mathcal{N})}$, so that $V(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{(\mathcal{N})})$, where \mathcal{N} denotes the PU copies' tessellation indices.
2. *Simulation Domain* (SD): Let a SD be a purely geometrical, continuous and deformable object (e.g. 1D curves, 2D surfaces, 3D volumes), with a parametrically defined ground state $\mathbf{x}_{sd}(\mathbf{s}_{sd})$.
3. *Tessellation & Periodicity Dimensionality* (PD): Let the PD denote the number of chosen tessellation directions of a continuous, monohedral and congruent objective tessellation for the chosen SD object. Let $\mathcal{N} = \{a, b, \dots\}$ represent the set of integer indices denoting the number of SD units along the tessellation directions, with $\mathcal{N} = \{0, 0, \dots\}$ referring to the core, initial SD.
4. *Kinematic Behaviour* (KB): Associate with the SD a continuous distribution of generalised properties, governed by a parametric vector function, $\mathbf{Y}_{sd}^{\mathbf{u}}$, which is dependent on n_e arbitrary free *kinematic parameters* \mathbf{e} . Thus the SD deformed state is described by $\mathbf{r}_{sd}(\mathbf{x}_{sd}, \mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{x}_{sd} + \mathbf{Y}_{sd}^{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}_{sd}, \mathbf{e})$.

3.4 1st Order Objective Boundary Conditions

The 1st order formulation of the OBC applies to UC with strictly local physics, i.e. $V(\mathbf{r})$, with overlapping material points at its boundaries, depicted by \bullet in Fig. 3(a). Hence, the PU boundary deformation profile, as locally observed from two corresponding points A and A^* on the SD object, must be identical up to and including orthogonal transformations. This condition may be stated as:

$$\mathbf{r}_{i^*} - \mathbf{r}_{A^*}(\mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{U}_A^{A^*}(\mathbf{e}) [\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_A(\mathbf{e})], \quad (4)$$

where i and i^* denote corresponding material points, and the unitary matrix, $\mathbf{U}_A^{A^*} = \mathbf{U}_A^{A^*}(\mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{O}_A (\mathbf{O}_{A^*})^{-1}$, describes the relative orthogonal rotation between the SD spacial orientations at the points A and A^* , denoted by \mathbf{O}_A and \mathbf{O}_{A^*} , which are readily obtained from the spacial gradient of the KB parametric function $\mathbf{r}_{sd}(\mathbf{x}_{sd}, \mathbf{e})$. For multi-physics domains, a generalised version of Eq. (4) of identical form holds. Eq. 4 may be enforced by any constraint method of choice (e.g. Lagrange multipliers, penalty method).

Figure 3: 1st order OBC enforces local boundary equivalence at corresponding boundaries.

3.5 2nd Order Objective Boundary Conditions

The 2nd order formulation of the OBC applies to UC with non-local physics, i.e. $V(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}^{(\mathcal{N})}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}))$. Using the SD points A and A^* , tessellations of a non-local material point i , denoted $i(\mathcal{N})$, are mapped by:

$$\mathbf{r}_{i(\mathcal{N})}(\mathbf{r}_{i(0)}, \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = \mathbf{r}_A(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) + \sum_{i=0}^{|\mathcal{A}|} (\mathbf{U}_A^{A^*}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}))^i [\mathbf{r}_{A^*}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}) - \mathbf{r}_A(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})] + (\mathbf{U}_A^{A^*}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}))^{|\mathcal{A}|} [\mathbf{r}_{i(0)} - \mathbf{r}_{A^*}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon})], \quad (5)$$

with analogous expressions for 2D and 3D tessellated UC. For the 3D case, the unitary matrices for all directions must be identity for a valid tessellation, so that the OBC reduce to PBC. Using Eq. (5), the non-local material point $\mathbf{r}_{i(\mathcal{N})}$ is mapped first, allowing for the standard evaluation of the non-local energy, Jacobian, $\mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}^V$, and Hessian, $\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}^V$. The latter non-local tensors contributions are mapped back to the core UC material point \mathbf{r}_i , using the transforms $\mathbf{J}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}$ obtained from Eq. (5), as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^V = \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}^V \mathbf{J}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{H}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^V = \left(\mathbf{J}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})} \right)^T \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}^V \mathbf{J}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})} + \mathbf{H}_{[\mathbf{q} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}]}^{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})} \mathbf{J}_{\mathbf{q}(\mathcal{N})}^V. \quad (6)$$

For multi-physics domains, generalised versions of Eq. (5) and (6) of identical form hold. Compared to the 1st order OBC, the current formulation requires more computational effort, but does not require a constraint equation approach and often results in faster and stabler numerical solver behaviour. The element topologies for non-local energies do not physically correspond to their interaction, but reduce to the set of core UC materials points required and an external node with the free *kinematic parameters*.

Figure 4: Non-local element topologies do not physically match the interaction they represent.

3.6 Implicit Property Homogenisation through OBC

Both the 1st and 2nd order OBC applied to systems described by Eq. (2), where the global solution minimises not only the PU generalised coordinates, \mathbf{q} , but the SD *kinematic parameters*, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, as well. If the KB parametric function, $\mathbf{r}_{\text{sd}}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{sd}}, \boldsymbol{\epsilon})$, respects the kinematic assumptions of a structural theory (e.g. plate theory), and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ are chosen to coincide with the theory's strain components, then the homogenised stress state and thereby the constitutive relations are implicitly obtained during the energy minimisation as the generalised forces corresponding to $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$. The modular composition of the OBC UC allows for the homogenisation of a PU as objects of varying dimensionality, form and kinematic behaviour, see Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Properties of physical units may be homogenised for different structural idealisations.

4 IMPLEMENTATION

The presented MDFEM and OBC formulations were implemented symbolically in MATLAB. A *Force Field Library* contains a range of MD force fields, while an *Element Library* stores all available characteristic variable definitions, and the OBC kinematic behaviour functions are user-specified. Using these libraries, the requested geometry is generated and meshed with all required elements before all MDFEM and OBC tensors are symbolically derived and analytically optimised¹. The resultant algebraic expressions are further optimised numerically, and exported in FORTRAN-90/95 format, which is suitable for the implicit and explicit FEM package ABAQUS as detailed elsewhere [1].

5 APPLICATIONS

5.1 Equivalence of MD and MDFEM: Brittle Failure of Carbon Nanotubes with Defects

The MDFEM obtains constitutive fracture responses of CNT with vacancies, Stone-Wales and weakened-bond defects in a highly non-linear environment during both static and dynamic implicit FE analyses [1]. The latter are equivalent to those of a MD study [17], see Fig. 7(a), but are obtained at computationally reduced cost; merely taking $\mathcal{O}(10^1 - 10^2)$ CPU seconds on a standard workstation.

Figure 6: MDFEM and MD obtain equivalent constitutive fracture responses for defective CNT.

5.2 MDFEM Linear computational scaling, eigenvalue analyses & solver strategy flexibility

The implicit static MDFEM exhibits linearly scaling numerical performance, as shown by axially straining CNT up to 1.0 million atoms, i.e. $12\ \mu\text{m}$ length, see Fig. 7(a). The implicit dynamic MDFEM solver, unlike an explicit dynamic MD, guarantees converged dynamic equilibrium at highly non-linear points (e.g. fracture onset, see Fig. 6(c)). Moreover, varied solver strategies are available (e.g. eigenvalue analyses for determining electric-field induced vibrational frequencies of molecular devices such as CNT), see Fig. 7(b), which MDFEM can model in sizes comparable to experimental results [1].

Figure 7: MDFEM has linear scaling and a broad range of solver strategies, e.g. eigenvalue analyses.

¹Model's Implementation Software will be made available at: www.imperial.ac.uk/people/silvestre.pinho

5.3 Electro-Mechanical MDFEM: Charge Densities & Electric Field Induced Polarisation

The MDFEM [1], when implemented with advanced anisotropic-polarisation charge-dipole [15], and reactive force fields [14], accurately captures electro-mechanical effects, such as charge induced mechanical strains in CNT, charge distributions in CNT deposited on substrates, pseudo-magnetic fields, electric field induced deflections and vibrations of graphene and CNT. Hence, the virtual design of such electro-mechanical nano-systems within the FEM is rendered possible, see Fig. 8.

(a) Charged graphene sheet's normalised charge density (b) Electric-field induced polarisation in an insulated CNT

Figure 8: MDFEM is ideally suited to design electro-mechanical devices towards target specifications.

5.4 MDFEM Multi-Scale: Hierarchical & Concurrent Integration of MD and FEM Domains

The MDFEM is ideally suited for hierarchical or concurrent multiscale coupling with continuum FEM, see Fig. 9, by avoiding the need for coupling separate numerical solvers and thus allowing for further computational savings. The proposed MDFEM [1] and OBC [2] formulations may be coupled with most existing coupling or hand-shake approaches for smoothing numerical mesh-transitions.

Figure 9: MDFEM achieves further computational savings by concurrently integrating continuum FEM & MD simulations within one solver, such as of this CNT with a discrete defect during fracture.

5.5 MDFEM & OBC Property Homogenisation: Graphene and 3D Pillared Graphene Structures

Using MDFEM and both 1st and 2nd order OBC, the properties of graphene and a Pillared Graphene Structure (PGS) were homogenised based on a SD with a *Kinematic Behaviour* consistent with classical Kirchoff plate theory. Hence, the *kinematic parameters* correspond to the plate strains, i.e. in-plane strains/shear/bending/twist, and the homogenised properties are reported as the typical **A** [TPa-nm] and **D** [TPa-nm³] matrices, as to avoid ambiguities with the thickness and continuum assumptions.

Table 1: Homogenised Mechanical In-Plane & Bending Properties of Graphene and PGS

	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{22}	A_{33}	D_{11}	D_{12}	D_{22}	D_{33}
G	0.2242	0.0182	0.2242	0.4044	0.1294×10^{-3}	-	0.1294×10^{-3}	N/A
PGS	0.3392	0.0731	0.3905	0.6409	0.0618	0.1654	0.0735	0.0680

Figure 10: MDfEM can parametrically design novel material nano-structures towards target properties, such as this undeformed PGS unit cell shown in pure shear (top/side-view) and bending.

While the PGS's and graphene's in-plane stiffness (\mathbf{A}) is of the same order of magnitude, the bending properties (\mathbf{D}) of the PGS are more than two orders of magnitude higher than those of graphene. No twist rigidity is presented for graphene as the used force field does is not applicable for linear twist. Fig. 10 shows that during pure shear as well as bending, the initial small in-plane waviness of the PGS is amplified. Lithium-doped PGS are predicted to possess unrivalled H_2 storage capacities at ambient conditions [6]. Hence, the MDfEM [1] and OBC [2], with their ability to incorporate both advanced mechanical and polarisable charge-dipole force fields, are ideally suited to perform parametric topology studies of the homogenised electro-mechanical, fracture and H_2 storage properties of such hybrid PGS.

5.6 MDfEM Macro-Scale Simulations: Stress Intensity Factor & Toughness of Graphene

The MDfEM computational scaling allows for modelling graphene sheets with 1-2 million atoms and above, i.e. macro-sized dimensions up to 0.2-0.5 μm corresponding to experimental flake sizes. The stress intensity factors and fracture toughness of graphene was obtained using (i) a macro-sized MDfEM simulation of a pre-cracked graphene sheet together with a crack compliance approach, see Fig. 11(a); (ii) a corresponding continuum shell model, based on homogenised properties, where the toughness is obtained through a J-integral approach around the crack opening, see Fig. 11(b); (iii) an analytical model based on chemical bond dissociation energy of sp^2 C-C, see Fig. 11(c). The obtained toughness, in unambiguous energy per unit length dimensions, are consistent across all three numerical approaches, see table 2, although these remain at half of recent experimental results; the discrepancy is likely due to the experimental measurements being on double-layered multi-grain graphene, rather than single-layered mono-grain graphene.

Figure 11: MDfEM can obtain large-scale properties such as toughness through macro-simulations.

Table 2: Graphene Toughness from MDfEM, Continuum, and Analytical Modelling are consistent.

	MDfEM Crack Opening	Continuum Shell J-Integral	Analytical Model	Experimental Measurements [18]
2D G_{Ic} (nJ/m)	2.42	2.69	2.50	5.41

5.7 MDFEM Device Design: Porous Graphene Membrane for DNA Sensor or Desalination

MDFEM is a computationally favourable and powerful framework for designing electro-mechanical nano-system within the virtual engineering design environment of FEM, while accurately capturing the physical mechanism described by MD. Fig. 12 shows a graphene device, where atoms (e.g. potassium, calcium) pass through a pore in the membrane, which may be used for single-molecule DNA sequencing, with the DNA-bases identified from the membrane's charge response, or as a desalination membrane.

The device's electro-mechanical response, including the long-range charge/dipole interactions between the thermally oscillating membrane and the non-carbon atoms, is accurately captured. The device was modelled using an implicit dynamic MDFEM, which offers some of the most distinctive features of the latter relative to MD. These include: (i) guaranteed converged dynamic equilibrium solutions, even in highly unstable conditions (e.g. fracture onset); (ii) stabler time stepping than in an explicit integration procedure; (iii) the ability to have singular mass matrices and thus concurrently solve designs with mechanical displacement, which have an inertial term, as well as multi-physics charge/dipole displacements, which physically do not have inertial properties. Such conditions require a self-consistent two-step solver approach in MD; a requirement which is removed and simplified to a one-step approach in MDFEM. The details of the electro-mechanical response of this device will be presented at the conference.

Figure 12: MDFEM can design electro-mechanical devices with good computational flexibility.

6 CONCLUSION

A *Molecular Dynamics Finite Element Method* (MDFEM) has been presented, together with novel boundary conditions, the *Objective Boundary Conditions* (OBC). While the novelty of the MDFEM formulation lies in its formal generalisation to multi-physics, the key novelty of the OBC concerns their modular formalism, which allows them to account for orthogonal periodicity in low-dimensional 1D/2D systems, while homogenising the response of such systems for any chosen structural idealisation theory.

The proposed MDFEM and OBC formulation: (i) has been shown to be exactly equivalent to MD; (ii) has produced novel mechanical and charge-dipole FEM results; (iii) allows for low-dimensional UC under novel rotational or orthogonal periodicity; (iv) homogenises the response of low-dimensional UC for any chosen structural idealisation; (v) does not require artificial kinetic co-energies of energy forms with no physical momenta, i.e. allowing a singular generalised mass matrix \mathbf{M} ; (vi) is computationally more favourable than MD with a linear numerical scaling; (vii) offers a broader range of analyses techniques over wider length and time scales; (viii) is inherently well-suited for multi-scale integration; (ix) is applicable to any chemical structure; (x) is applicable for both zero and finite temperatures.

The proposed model represents a unified formulation of MD bridging from small to large time and spacial scales, as well as across different physics, while inherently offering convenient multi-scale and homogenisation integration with continuum FEM. It will allow for the optimised virtual design of a wide range of electro-mechanical nano-devices and structures to either given device property or macroscopic target specifications (e.g. piezoelectric property couplings in CNT, H_2 storage in PGS), and homogenised properties for different homo- and heteroatomic nano-structures to be used in industrial applications (e.g. structural composites, DNA sensors, flexible electronics).

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